

A study on late time UV-emission in core collapse supernovae and the implications for the peculiar transient AT2018cow

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ABSTRACT

Context. Over time, core-collapse supernova (CCSN) spectra become redder due to dust formation and cooling of the SN ejecta. An ultraviolet (UV) detection of a CCSN at late times thus indicates an additional physical process such as interaction between the SN ejecta and the circumstellar material, or viewing down to the central engine of the explosion. Both these models have been proposed to explain the peculiar transient AT2018cow, a luminous fast blue optical transient that has been detected in the UV 2–4 years after the event with only marginal fading over this time period.

Aims. To identify if the late-time UV detection of AT2018cow could indicate that it is a CCSN, we investigate if CCSNe are detected in the UV between 2–5 years after the explosion. We determine how common late-time UV emission in CCSNe is and compare those CCSNe detected in the UV to the peculiar transient AT2018cow.

Methods. We use a sample of 51 nearby ($z < 0.065$) CCSNe observed with the *Hubble Space Telescope* within 2–5 years of discovery. We measure their brightness, or determine an upper limit on the emission through an artificial star experiment if there is no detection.

Results. For two CCSNe we detect a point source within the uncertainty region of the SN position. Both have a low chance alignment probability with bright objects within their host galaxies and are therefore likely related to the SNe, both of which are known to be interacting supernovae.

Conclusions. Comparing the absolute UV magnitude of AT2018cow at late times to the absolute UV magnitudes of the two potential SN detections, there is no evidence that a late-time UV detection of AT2018cow is atypical for interacting SNe. However, when limiting the sample to CCSNe closer than AT2018cow, we see that it is brighter than the upper limits on most CCSN non-detections. Combined with a very small late time photospheric radius of AT2018cow, this leads us to conclude that AT2018cow's late-time UV detection was not driven by interaction. It suggests instead that we are possibly viewing the inner region of the explosion, perhaps due to the long-lived presence of an accretion disc. Such properties are naturally expected in tidal disruption models and are less straightforward (though not impossible) in supernova scenarios.

Key words. stars: massive – stars: individual: AT2018cow – ultraviolet: stars – supernovae: general

Appendix B: Supernova positions and uncertainties

Fig. B.1. Mosaic showing different size cutouts of all SNe in our sample where we did not detect a point source within the 3σ positional uncertainty region. The cutouts are centred on the SN positions. The 1, 2 and 3σ errors on the position is shown by the red circles. The white lines indicate a length of $1''$ (or $4''$ if the 1σ uncertainty region is $1''$, separated on the bottom row). For all images North is up and East is left. The scale of the pixel values was chosen to show any structure present in the emission.

Appendix C: SN2018ant individual frames

Fig. C.1. Mosaic showing the $2'' \times 2''$ cutout of the position of SN2018ant in the top row, its individual `_f1c` images in the middle row and the same individual `_f1c` images after masking by DOLPHOT in the bottom row. The cutouts are centred on the SN position. The 1, 2 and 3σ error on the source position is indicated by the red circles in each image. The white line indicates a length of $1''$. For all images North is up and East is left. The scale of the pixel values was arbitrarily chosen.

Appendix D: Sources closer than AT2018cow

Fig. D.1. Same as Figure 2, but showing only the sources with a distance closer than the distance to AT2018cow.